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Graphene based nanocomposites for tribological application

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Outline

➤ **Background**

Graphene, a new emerging solid lubricant

- **High wear-resistance of graphene/PVC composites**
- **High-performance graphene-based lubricating oil**
- **Summary**

Graphene Materials

Structure

Fabrication

Performance

- High electrical conductivity
- Large aspect ratio, $\sim 10^6$
- Large current density, 10^9A/cm^2
- High modulus, $\sim 1 \text{TPa}$
- High thermal conductivity, 4000W/(m.K)
- Large surface area
- Low friction coefficient, 0.15-0.2

Potential application

Large-scale application?

Graphene: a new emerging lubricant

Extremely high strength
High chemical inertness
Easy shear capability on densely-packed and atomically-smooth surface

Overview of macroscale tribological properties of widely used solid lubricants.

Solid lubricant coating	Deposition methods	Coating thickness (μm)	Typical friction coefficient	Wear/friction mechanism
Graphite	Evaporation, pyrolysis	0.2–5	Dry: 0.5–0.6; Humid: 0.1–0.2	Interlayer shear and water intercalation
Diamond like carbon (near frictionless carbon)	Sputtering (rf and dc), ion-beam, PECVD	1–3	Dry: 0.001–0.05; Humid: 0.2–0.3	High chemical inertness and repulsive forces due to hydrogen termination
Tetrahedral amorphous carbon	Ion beam, cathodic arc, pulsed laser	0.01–1	Dry: 0.7; Humid: 0.1	Tribochemically induced surface reaction and termination of top carbon atoms
Ultrananocrystalline diamond	MPCVD, HFCVD	0.5–1.5	Dry: 0.05–0.13; Humid: 0.007–0.1	Tribochemically induced reaction with H, O, or OH
MoS ₂ and WS ₂	Sputtering (rf and dc), thermal evaporation CVD, ALD	0.2–2	Dry: 0.02–0.06; Humid: 0.15–0.25 initial and increasing	Interlayer shear and transfer film formation
Graphene/graphene oxide	CVD, chemical and mechanical exfoliation	0.001–0.002	Dry: 0.15–0.2; Humid: 0.15–0.2	Interlayer shear and prevention of tribocorrosion

Motivation

To explore commercial application of graphene in composite fields by virtue of excellent tribological characteristics of graphene

- (1) To obtain graphene/PVC composites with high wear-resistance.
- (2) To improve tribological performance of Lubricating oil with addition of graphene.

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Poly(vinyl chloride), PVC

- One of the most widely-used materials
- High mechanical strength
- Good fire-retardance
- Good chemical resistance
- Low cost

➤ **Existing problem**

- Rigid PVC are typically brittle
- Some microcracks are easily generated and propagated under friction stress

➤ **Solving method**

- Extraordinary self-lubricant characteristics of graphene, due to its unique flexible graphitic layers, extremely high strength, and easy shear capability on its densely packed and atomically smooth surface.

➤ **Aim**

To obtain graphene/PVC composites with high tribological performance

Cable

Construction

Decoration

Pipes

Experimental

Materials: Commercial multi-layer graphene (MLG), produced by using intercalation and thermal expansion exfoliation methods, supplied from Sichuan Jinlu Group Co. Ltd. China

- ✓ Average thickness is 5-8 graphitic layers (1-5 nm)
- ✓ Lateral size of 10- 15 μm
- ✓ High purity of over 97% (C/O ratio more than 20)
- ✓ Electrical conductivity is over 700 S/cm
- ✓ Wrinkled and crumpled morphology
- ✓ High flexibility due to large aspect ratio

J Mater Sci Technol 2015, 31(4):340

Polym Compos 2016, Online.

Experimental

Fabrication of MLG/PVC composites

Conventional melt-mixing, calendaring & hot-pressing methods

Measurement

Morphology, microstru

Mechanical properties, micro-hardness, tribological properties

Microstructure of MLG/PVC composites

- Uniform dispersion of MLG throughout PVC matrix
- Brittle fracture of neat PVC
- Coarse fracture surface of the MLG/PVC composites indicates ductile fracture

Microhardness of the MLG/PVC composites

- Lower hardness of the MLG/PCV composites than neat PVC
- High flexibility of the crumpled MLG

Friction coefficient of the MLG/PVC composites

Friction coefficient =
friction force/applied load

Molecular-mechanical
theory of dry sliding
friction of plastics

Wear rate of the MLG/PVC composites

Adhesive wear theory of plastics

Wear mechanism of the MLG/PVC composites

The presence of MLG can greatly improve the wear resistance of the MLG/PVC composites, which is mainly attributed to high toughness and high self-lubricant performance of the MLG.

Worn surface morphology of the MLG/PVC composites

Summary (1)

- **The presence of graphene can enhance toughness of the MLG/PVC composites due to high flexibility of the crumpled MLG and rich interfaces of nanocomposites**
- **The MLG/PVC composites exhibited much lower friction coefficient and wear rate than the neat PVC, indicating that the presence of MLG can greatly improve the wear resistance of the MLG/PVC composites, which is mainly attribute to the enhanced toughness of the nanocomposites and high self-lubricant performance of the MLG.**

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Friction

Damage

Lubrication: Control friction and wear
Improve efficiency of machine
Reduce loss of energy
Reduce consumption of materials
Ensure working reliability of machine

Lubrication regimes

- ✓ Improving strength of oil films
- ✓ Increasing oil-adsorption on surfaces
- ✓ Reducing friction coefficient
- ✓ Lowering abrasion mass

$f \approx 0.1 \sim 0.3$

$f \approx 0.005 \sim 0.1$

$f \approx 0.001 \sim 0.01$

Lubricants

✦ A good lubricant should carry a number of advantages, including:

1. Better stability is observed while suspended in base oils as compared to macro or micro particles.
2. Nanoparticles enter the contact area easily and also provide a protective coating against wear.
3. Nanoparticles do not require an induction period to obtain the desired tribological properties as they are often efficient at ambient temperature, unlike their micro counterparts.
4. Nanoparticles possess better thermo-physical properties than their bulk counterparts.

Existing problems & solving strategy

Dependence on size and morphology of graphene

To realize good dispersion of graphene in oil

Poor compatibility between graphene and base oil

Tuning morphology for obtaining satisfied tribological performance

Low dispersion stability of graphene-based oil

Unsatisfied friction coefficients and tribological properties

To obtain high-performance lubricating oil

Motivation

- ✓ Average thickness is 5-8 graphitic layers (1-5 nm)
- ✓ Lateral size of 15- 20 μm
- ✓ Wrinkled and crumpled morphology
- ✓ High flexibility due to large aspect ratio

It can be flattened, crumpled, hollowed...

Morphology of graphene definitely plays an important role

How about the tribological performance?

Experimentals

Raw materials:

Graphene: graphene nanosheet (GNS) with average diameter of 15 μm .

Lubricating Oil: base oil B250S, Jiangshu Huifeng lubricant Co, Ltd.

Characterization:

SEM and Optical microscopy for morphology observation;
Size distribution using Malvin 2000 laser particle size analyzer.

Measurement:

ASTM D 4172

Size and morphology regulation

Size control

Large-scale industrial production

Formation mechanism of graphene ball

Crumpled graphene balls (CGB)

Hollow graphene balls (HGB)

Oil absorption capability of the hollow graphene balls

Dispersion of graphene in oil

After 48 h

Tribological properties

Friction coefficient

Tribological properties

Optical micrographs of wear scars of the ball counterparts

660 μm

Base oil

534 μm

0.025 mg/ml HGB/oil

498 μm

0.05 mg/ml HGB/oil

459 μm

0.075 mg/ml HGB/oil

431 μm

0.1 mg/ml HGB/oil

Wear scar diameter (WSD)

Tribological properties

Wear scar diameter (WSD) →

Friction coefficient

Extraordinary self-lubricating characteristic
Intrinsic low friction coefficient
Narrow size distribution
Good compatibility and stability

Summary (2)

- The addition of graphene can greatly improve tribological performance of base oil due to extraordinary lubricating characteristics of graphene.
- The tribological properties of graphene-based oil strongly depends on size, morphology, compatibility, and dispersion of graphene.
- There is great potential for graphene to be used as high-performance lubricants in many industrial fields.

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